

Shimglina Customary Conflict Resolution Mechanism for Rural Land Disputes in Ethiopia: The Practice and Challenges

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Abstract

Rural land disputes were instigated due to various factors like the increases in population number, scarcity of farm land, poverty, increase in rural land value, and weak rural land administration system, which were the indirect causes and manifested in the forms of boundary disputes, inheritances disputes, transfer of land disputes, access, and ownership disputes. This study indicates that different variants of Shimglina customary conflict resolution mechanisms are playing a significant role resolving in rural land disputes. Shimglina prevents violence too. The social capital and social solidarity of the community is functional under the umbrella of Shimglina and vice versa. Shimglina is vital to resolving conflict and disputes in terms of its attachment with the living God, value of perpetual peace, reduction of time to decide on the issue, resource and its accessibility to all members of the community, and restoring peaceful interaction. This study reveals that Shimglina faced many challenges that hinder its effectiveness in the resolution of rural land disputes. Unless the underlying challenges of Shimglina are solved, the effectiveness of the mechanism in the resolution of rural land dispute is difficult. Thus, the absence of clear legal and policy framework in the practices of Shimglina, lack of support and encouragements to the Shimglina culture of peace by the government, the absence of strong enforcement mechanism for the decision of elders, the influence and intervention of government bodies and politicization of Shimglina culture are the challenges in the practices of Shimglina in rural land disputes resolution. The local and regional governments should work to advance Shimglina peace culture for rural land disputes settlement, peaceful co-existence, and community solidarity.

Keywords

Rural Land; Disputes; Traditional/customary conflict resolution; Challenges to customary/traditional conflict resolution; Peace, Shimglina, Peace lovers

1. Introduction

Ethiopia is an ethnically diverse country, home to many ethnic and tribal groups, each with its own customary conflict resolution mechanisms. These practices are used to settle various disputes within their communities, at individual and group levels alike (Esayas, 2015; Gonfa, 2014; Regassa, 2008). In Ethiopia, the customary conflict resolution practices are mostly utilized in rural areas where the formal legal system struggles to penetrate due to a lack of resources, infrastructure and legal personnel. Additionally, the modern legal system often lacks legitimacy in these regions, as it is seen as unusual, imposed, and out of touch with the cultural realities of the local population. The modern legal system is also criticized for being unaware of the impact its decisions could have on the relationships between disputing parties. Accordingly, in such circumstances, the customary dispute resolution mechanisms play a vital role in the administering justice and resolving disputes in rural communities (Endalew, 2014).

In case of the Amhara people, the procedure and practices of Shimglina (elderliness) is a key conflict resolution mechanism. Here, elders, referred to as *Shemagles*, are the custodians of orally transmitted customary norms known as *Yeabat ager hig* (the law of the land of the fathers). The dispute resolution process is practiced based on the tradition and knowledge of elders (Yoseph, 2006). As such, Shimglina has been the most commonly used form of dispute resolution mechanism in the Amhara society from ancient times (Mulugeta & Tefere, 2009). The community recognizes and carefully chooses Shimglina committee of elders as the most effective mechanism to settle disputes in the community based on its long-established norms and values (Getachew, 1998). The major activities of the *shimageles* involve mediating and reconciling conflicting parties, including extended members of the disputants, to create peaceful relationships based on societal values and norms (Wondyrad, 2014). Moreover, the religious leaders also play a vital role in Shimglina, working alongside local elders.

Another important institution in the Amhara community is *Yezemed Dagna* (family arbitrator). The arbitrators, who are family members, work to resolve disputes that arise within families. Their primary function is to bring disputing parties to an amicable solution, thereby enabling them to avoid court cases that might further damage precarious relationships (Mulugeta & Tefere, 2009, 2009) of the disputants. As far as the land and land-related dispute resolution mechanisms among the Amhara people are concerned, village elders and religious leaders play a significant role in resolving these issues and making Shimglina the foremost dispute settlement mechanism available to them. According to estimates, about 80 per cent of the rural community resorts to customary dispute resolution mechanisms through *shimageles* (village elders and religious leaders) (World Bank, 2012).

In the Amhara, the Revised Amhara National Regional State Rural Land Administration and Use Proclamation, in its Proclamation No.133/2006, deals with settlement of land disputes at the rural level. Article 29 of the Proclamation deals with disputes related to rural land issues. In this region, no civil dispute arising from the holding or use of rural land can be submitted to a regular court before it is submitted to a customary dispute resolution mechanism, and the outcome of such a mechanism must be known (Mequanent, 2016; Shewakena, 2007). Towards this end, the government has established elders' arbitration committees (EAC), locally known as "*ye-shemaglewoch shengo*", which is supported by the land administration unit in the *kebeles* (the smallest unit of local government in Ethiopia) and run by a local-level land administration expert to resolve land and related disputes in the local community (Gashu & Amsalu, 2017). Residents in the selected *kebeles* of district (woreda) of Bahir Dar Zuria face recurrent serious land disputes. The formal legal system is unable to resolve the disputes effectively (and it is not suited to the socially

interconnected life of the community). It does not address the root causes of the conflict. On the other hand, the researcher also observed many challenges in the practices of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes, which reduce their effectiveness, endanger their existence, and undermine the community's trust in these customary mechanisms.

Societies worldwide have long utilized customary conflict resolution mechanisms to address disputes between individuals, groups, and communities. These practices are deeply rooted in community customs (Macfarlane, 2006). In societies where poverty and widespread illiteracy limit access to justice, the high cost of modern systems of conflict resolution and the scarcity of lawyers make customary methods particularly attractive (Alemie and Hone, 2018). The formal legal system established by law often appears adversarial to the disputant and overlooks the consensus-based approach, which is at the heart of customary conflict resolution mechanisms (Luccaro, 2016). The objective of these mechanisms is to ensure that disputes are resolved effectively and efficiently, benefiting both disputants and the community by fostering harmonious relationships in the society (Luccaro, 2016).

One of the resources that has become a source of dispute across communities and countries is the limited availability of arable land. As such, land disputes have become increasingly common among individual farmers and investors because of its scarcity (Siyum et al., 2015). Such disputes hinder land use, development, peace and tenure security in Africa, particularly in sub-Saharan African countries, often leading to violent conflicts that often destroy communities, people's lives, and their livelihood (Niang and Dieng, 2004). In fact, "land disputes are very serious and fierce, nobody takes the matter flippantly, and hence any silly issues can result in big conflicts costing even the life of the disputants or resulting in injuries or costly court case proceedings" (Behailu, 2015: 139).

In Ethiopia, rural land disputes are regarded as a significant social problem requiring settlement mechanism that aligns with the social systems of a community (Bedasa and Hussein, 2018). Most of the rural population in Ethiopia relies on customary conflict resolution mechanisms to settle land disputes within their cultural context (Kassa, 2020). However, these mechanisms face challenges such as government interference and local cultural limitations, which impact their effectiveness in addressing rural land disputes (Girma, 2014). In the Amhara region, the majority of farmers have experienced land disputes due to problems of inheritance, boundary-setting, land transfer and divorce (Shibeshi et al., 2015). Moreover, Zerihun (2016) notes that the current rural land proclamations fail to resolve these land disputes effectively in Ethiopia. In this situation, reinforcing customary dispute resolution mechanisms could be crucial in addressing land disputes. According to Solomon (1992), Yohannes (2003), and Yoseph (2006), the customary law applied among the Amhara people is an unwritten custom called *Shimglina*, which effectively resolves various types of disputes, including rural land disputes. *Shimglina*, or elder-based mediation, is the most common form of dispute resolution mechanism at the local community level. Besides elders, religious leaders also play a key role in dispute resolution in many parts of Amhara Region (Getachew, 1998). In light of the importance of this type of dispute resolution, this study examines the practice of *Shimglina* as a customary conflict resolution mechanism and its challenges in resolving rural land disputes in the district (woreda) of Dar Zuria.

The objective of this study is to examine the practices and challenges of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute in the study area. The goal is to provide recommendations for policymakers, community leaders, and land administrators who are intimately involved in addressing these issues in these communities.

2. Methodology

The study employed a qualitative research design, focusing on community beliefs, opinions, experiences, and relationships, and cultural and social phenomena regarding the practices and challenges of Shimglina customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes in the study area. The researcher used purposive sampling to select focus group discussion (FGD) participants and key informants from the kebeles. These kebeles were selected based on preliminary data from the rural land administration office concerning land and land-related disputes.

The study was conducted from 2019 to 2020. The participants included elders, religious leaders, Woreda court judges, land administration experts from the woreda and kebeles, members of the land administration committee, landholding farmers who had settled their land disputes through customary conflict resolution mechanisms, and experts from the Amhara region land administration. The study focused on five rural kebeles of Bahir Dar Zuria Woreda, specifically targeting residents of Wojer, Sebatamet, Tentakerkose, Feresewoga and Lijome Kebeles. The collected data was analyzed based on content presentation and interpreted according to thematic areas relevant to this study.

Table 1: Number of FGD participants in the study area kebeles

<i>FGD Participants</i>	<i>Number of Kebeles</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
Kebeles	5	
Wojer		7
Tentakerkose		8
Lijome		6
Sebatamet		9
Feresewoga		8
Total		38

Table 2: Participants of key informant interview

<i>Key interview participants</i>	<i>Number of participants from the study area kebeles</i>
Elders	15
Religious leaders	10
Woreda court judges	2
Land administration experts from the Woreda	2
Land administration experts from kebeles	5
Members of the land administration committee	7
Farmers who had settled their land disputes	11
Experts from the Amhara region land administration	3
Total	55

2.1 Area of the Study

Bahir Dar Zuria Woreda is located in the West Gojjam Administrative Zone of Amhara National Regional State of Ethiopia. The woreda shares boundaries with Lake Tana to the north, Achefir Woreda to the east, Dera Woreda to the east, and Yilmana Densa Woreda to the south. It comprises of 36 rural kebeles with a total population of 202,960 (DOA, 2000).

2.2 Theoretical Grounds for Conflict Resolution by Customary or Ingenious Mechanisms

There are theories that support conflict resolution through customary mechanisms involving elders, based on the cultural norms and values of a society. Some of the important theories that clarify the nature and significance of these customary or indigenous mechanisms are given below.

Figure 1: Map of the study area

2.2.1. Social Capital Theory

Social capital theory emphasizes on shared norms, relationships, reciprocal obligations, trust, and the horizontal and vertical social networks that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutually beneficial collective action within a community. This theory highlights the importance of social capital as an asset that people rely on to resolve conflicts arising from social interactions in the community and incompatible interests of its members (Sanginga et al., 2007). It explains the restorative nature of dispute resolution by the elders in African societies where the aim is to restore the social ties (the social capital) that were broken due to disputes (Kariuki, 2015). The theory demonstrates how the community and local elders resolve disputes and reestablish social ties, contributing to peaceful relationships. It suggests that the success of the customary or indigenous mechanisms in aiding the process of conflict resolution and achieving peace depends on the existing social capital (Kariuki, 2015). In view of this theory, the Shimglina customary dispute resolution mechanism, adopted and utilized by the community, helps resolve land use and related disputes based on its long-established traditional social capital. There are other traditional practices in Ethiopia like *iddir* and *mahiber*, which also point to collective action that produce their own social capital.

2.2.2. Social Solidarity Theory

Social solidarity theory explains the importance of dispute resolution through customary mechanisms involving elders, especially in communities that do not prefer using formal dispute resolution mechanisms. These communities may dislike the

western legal system for creating problems in future relationships of disputants, dissatisfaction with the results, cost, time, and other factors. Therefore, customary practices of conflict resolution by elders are important to resolve the disputes within the community (Durkheim, 1984; Kariuki, 2015). According to this theory, individual members of a society are social actors controlled by social facts such as values, norms, and social structures. As such, dispute resolution by elders is perceived as a social fact from which a society benefits (Kariuki, 2015). In his theory of social action, Parsons (1991) argued that shared values and norms, provided by the cultural system of a society, support social order and harmony. In this context, shared value patterns are integrated into individuals' mindsets and actions through the process of internalization. Social integration in a society rests on a wide-ranging agreement on the long-established basic norms and values that contribute to peaceful co-existence. In this context, Murithi (2006: 13) argues that:

“An integral part of the process of achieving positive peace is the need to promote social solidarity. Achieving social solidarity means that members of the society once again begin to recognize each other as fellow human beings and begin to share a concern in the common welfare and well-being of each other. Social solidarity makes sense because only by ensuring the security, safety, and well-being of other people, can we hope to secure our own security, safety, and well-being. To emphasize the need to foster social solidarity is to recognize the interconnectedness of each human being.”

The social solidarity theory is essential for understanding and explaining the practices and challenges of Shimglina system of dispute resolution in rural land use and related disputes. It shows how Shimageles (elders and religious leaders) resolve disputes and how individuals and the community benefit from the Shimglina mechanism, based on their shared peace values and norms, which are integral to its practice and nature.

3. Practices of Shimglina

Farming communities in Bahir Dar Zuria Woreda have a history of using various variants of Shimglina customary conflict resolution to address their rural land disputes, as confirmed by interviews with regional land experts (interview with regional land expert 1 at Amhara Region Rural Land Administration and Use Bureau, 18 February 2020). Government documents also acknowledge that these customary conflict resolution mechanisms are utilized in resolving rural land disputes in the Amhara region, including Bahir Zuria Woreda. Various variants of *shimglina* customary conflict resolution mechanisms in Bahir Dar Zuria Woreda in particular (interview with elder 2 at Lijome *kebele*, 7 February 2020). Supporting this, the revised Rural Land Administration and Use Proclamation of Amhara National Regional State No.133/2006, Article 29/1, states, “any civil dispute that may arise in connection to land holding or using right shall priory be seen and resolved in arbitration” (ANRS Zikre Hig No. 18:30). Thus, this evidence indicates that customary conflict resolution mechanisms have essentially been established by the government for land disputes resolution at the *kebele* level.

As Shimglina is a committee of elders established to resolve different types of conflicts and disputes in society; it is regarded as a legitimate way to sustain peace among the disputants (Getachew, 1998; Solomon, 1992; Yohannes, 2003; Yoseph, 2006). Shimglina practices are diverse, including efforts at various levels, i.e., at the level of Kebel, village, neighborhood and family. It is the major and widely used conflict resolution mechanisms practiced to resolve rural land disputes (interview with elder 5 at Lijome *kebele*, 7 February 2020).

In the study area of the Amhara region, Shimglina is extensively practiced for resolving land disputes in its rural society (World Bank, 2012; Yohannes (2003). Informants asserted that the community in the study area uses Shimglina to handle land disputes at the grassroots level, leveraging the wisdom of *shimageles* (elders and religious leaders) to foster harmonious community life, reestablish peaceful interactions between disputing parties, and maintain community solidarity. One key informant argued: “In the institution of shimglina mediators and conciliators are residents within their community they are living. They work in the resolution of land disputes for the shared benefits of the disputant and for the general community, since they are closely connected with the disputants as a member of the community (interview with elder 4, who resolved his land disputes through shimglina at Sebatamet kebele, 11 February 2020)”.

In Ethiopia, given the importance of land as a prime resource for the Amhara people due to its scarcity, the community, as such, relies on its traditional institutions to resolve land and related disputes (World Bank, 2012). Equally, in the study area, various forms of Shimglina serve to resolve land and related disputes in the community, often more effectively than government disputes settlement institutions. Disputants choose from different variants of Shimglina based on their preferences (FGD1 with elders at Wojer Kebele, 9 February 2020). One of the FGD participants described it as:

“A mechanism to resolve land disputes to maintain the community in peace and stability based on its respected shared norm of the society that promotes forgiveness, tolerance, peaceful coexistence, respect and truthfulness are among others. The variants of the practices [like] shimglina customary conflict resolution mechanism are hierarchical in the community. The dispute resolution activity is guided by the traditional shared norms and values” (Interview with elder 6 at Tentakerkose kebele, 17 February 2020).

In this context, Kariuki (2015) explained that dispute resolution based on social facts (norms and values) is crucial for solidifying peaceful coexistence and restraining any prospective unwanted actions of the disputants, as dispute resolution by elders itself is a social fact. Therefore, individual disputants, as social actors, cannot be excluded from this process. Study participants revealed that there exist different hierarches of Shimglina in the Sub-Saharan Africa. The Kebele-level Shimglina is the highest, with *shimageles* at this level called *Yehager Shimagele*. These actors, selected from respected villagers, handle more serious escalated land disputes, particularly communal land disputes between the community and individuals. The community has the right to follow up the procedure of the reconciliation (interview with elder-3 and religious leader -1 at Lijome kebele, 24 February and 5 March 2020).

Figure 1: Levels of Shimglina customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes among the rural community in the study area (Source: Adapted from the collected data (6 March 2020)

The village-level Shimglina operates within village members or one *Iddir* (self-help association of the village). While *Iddir* primarily provides funeral related services, it now extends to dispute resolution among its members. In this self-help association, land disputes are governed based on their established norms and rules. The informants indicated that this level of Shimglina is more effective in resolving land disputes within village members (interview with elder 2 Feresewoga kebele, 5 February 2020). Additionally, the Shimglina at this level involves three chiefs of one *Iddir* (self-help association) and elders. As such, in this mechanism of dispute resolution, while it is mandatory to all members of the *Iddir* or villagers to attend meetings, they can also make suggestions to help address the issues. Reconciliation happens based on community values and the guilty is punished as per the specific rules of the *Iddir*, including through money.

The third level Shimglina operates at neighborhood level. It addresses disputes among neighbouring farmers interconnected through social ties such as friendship (*wodaje*), gratitude, kinship (*yekeristena li*), and marriage. This mechanism is effective to resolve disputes related to divorce-related land division, inheritance, cattle crop destruction, private grazing land, drainage directions, access to pathways, and plant shade that arise among neighbours (Interview with Elder 4 and Religious Leader 1 at Sebatamet Kebele, 23 February 2020). The fourth level of *Shimglina* is family level, or *yezemed danignet* (family arbitration), which is facilitated, negotiated, and reconciled through blood relatives and family members of the disputants (Getachew, 1998 and Yoseph, 2006). This form is significant for resolving intra-family land and related disputes arising from inheritance, divorce, donation, thereby playing a crucial role in the harmonious existence of families (Interview with Elder 3 at Tentakerkose kebele, 17 February 2020). This demonstrates that Shimglina contributes a great deal in the peaceful co-existence of families and their harmonious interactions in day-to-day social and economic engagements.

Figure 2: Procedures of *shimglina* in rural land dispute resolution [Source: Adapted from the field work data, 5 February 2020]

In addition to these mechanisms, the Amhara community utilizes social capital to resolve disputes (Birhanu, 2018). The study informants stated that some land disputes are resolved within *Iddir* and sometimes in Mahiber, which is another other variant of Shimglina. This indicates that the social capital of the community in the study area plays a crucial role in land dispute resolution. From all variants of Shimglina, it is evident that Shimglina fosters a culture of peace based on values, attitudes, traditions, norms, and the modes of behavior that shift disputants' mindset and behaviour from conflict to dialogue and eventually healing the wounds of the conflict to achieve peace. At this level of Shimglina, there is no separation of authority in the settlement of rural land disputes. Disputants have the right to take their cases to any level of Shimglina based on their preference. Shimglina significantly helps the community to restore broken social ties resulting from land disputes between individuals, groups and families (interview with elder-1 at Tentakerkose kebele, 5 February 2020).

4. Challenges to Shimglina's Dispute Settlement Mechanism

The data collected for this study also shows that Shimglina customary conflict resolution mechanism has encountered many challenges in settling rural land

disputes, negatively affecting their effectiveness (interview with elder-2 at Sebatamet *kebele*, 9 February 2020). These challenges stem from various factors, including primarily in designing appropriate policies and institutional frameworks that create conducive environment for an effective deployment of customary dispute resolution institutions in rural land disputes (Kassa, 2020; Girma, 2014; Mequanent, 2016). The challenges to Shimglina mechanism in resolving rural land disputes in the study area community are discussed below:

a. The Absence of Incentives

Shimglina conflict resolution through shimageles (elders and religious leaders) lacks incentives for their dispute resolution activities (Bamlak, 2013). Informants noted that the absence of encouragement negatively influences shimageles' interests and effectiveness. Perceiving it as their moral responsibility, they provide voluntary services, sacrificing their personal agricultural time for the community's peaceful existence. This is important given that agricultural activities by nature are time-consuming and hence providing such a voluntary service, particularly during peak farming seasons, assumes significance. As one informant stated, "We are unpaid judges resolving land disputes with our traditional wisdom, but the government does not support us financially" (FGD2 with the elderly arbitration committee at Feresewoga *kebele*, 11 February 2020). Consequently, the lack of financial support is a significant challenge for sustaining this form of dispute resolution given that majority of such disputes are resolved locally through these customary systems (Religious leader 2 at Sebatamet *kebele*, 23 February 2020).

b. The Influence of Globalization

With the onset of globalization, modern formal dispute resolution systems have introduced new ideas, affecting the community's perception of Shimglina. As such, young community members, who are more prone to be influenced by globalization and modern education, view Shimglina as an archaic and redundant dispute resolution mechanism. This has led the younger people to perceive these customary dispute resolution values negatively, whose respect is at the core of this traditional mechanism (interview with elder 3 at Wojer *kebele*, 9 February 2020). Consequently, educated young farmers, influenced by modern education, often violate Shimglina decisions. For instance, during the FGD2 with the Elderly Arbitration Committee at Feresewoga *kebele* on 11 February 2020, it emerged that:

"Young farmers in our area are more educated compared to the majority of the farmers, having completed at least 12 years of basic education 12th completed. Due to the influence of their modern education, they do not give desired respect and value to Shimglina system in addressing rural land disputes. Even though they were taking their land dispute to shimglina, they mostly end up violating not only the decisions of elders but also any other form of traditional understanding achieved to address their issues (FGD2 with the elderly arbitration committee at Feresewoga *kebele*, 11 February 2020)."

c. Lack of Governmental Attention

In developing countries, the significance of customary strategies is often undermined by politicization, corruption, and abuse of traditional structures, reducing confidence in their efficiency (Boege, 2006; Kariuki, 2015). The government gives low attention to Shimglina in rural land dispute resolution. In developing countries, the significance and practical implementation of customary strategies is often undermined by politicization, corruption, and abuse of traditional structures, thereby gradually affecting their popular perception and reducing confidence in their efficiency (Boege, 2006 and Kariuki, 2015). Besides, its challenges have been compounded by the lack of government attention to Shimglina as a land dispute resolution mechanism. As two informants of the study affirm:

"In our area, Shimglina in general, and Shimageles (elders and religious leaders) in particular, are given less attention by the government in settling rural land disputes. For the advancement of Shimglina in resolving various rural land and

related disputes, government support and promotion are very significant. Despite this, the government focuses on informing the community about formal mechanisms of rural land dispute resolution institutions rather than encouraging the use of local mechanisms, such as Shimglina. The government does not recognize the work of elders and religious leaders in land dispute resolutions and only calls upon us when such disputes escalate. While we calm down situations and resolve disputes, but soon after, the government forgets us. Moreover, the government uses us for political input to interact with the community and protect its interest in land-related issues (interview with elder 4 and religious leader 2 at Tentakerkose kebele, 24 February 2020).

As such, it emerges that the governmental preference for formal mechanisms over encouraging local dispute resolution has emerged as a major hindrance to the effectiveness of these traditional dispute mechanisms, which are used only when disputes escalate and more often for political purposes.

d. Inability to Mediate in Land Disputes involving Government

Notwithstanding its utility in dispute resolution, there is a limitation in the Shimglina mechanism in settling disputes between individuals, the community, and the government beyond a certain extent. According to some research informants, Shemegles often struggle to effectively tackle issues of land expropriation and its valuation because of lack of laws and rules to address such problems. These issues often emerged when the government expropriated rural lands held by individuals and communities for various purposes such as establishing factories or such other industrial firms without providing fair compensation at respectable valuation (interview with Woreda Land Administration experts). These disputes are resolved by government-established grievance hearing committees, which lack neutrality and always favour the government. As a land administration expert summarizes:

“The problems occurred due to the fact that the government did not allow the issue to be resolved through Shimglina by Shimageles. The disputes were resolved by the governmentally established grievance hearing committee in the rural land administration and use offices. The problem here is those committee members are political appointees who lack neutrality in their decision and prioritize the interest of the government only to the disadvantage of locals (interview with elder 2 at Tentakerkose kebele, 15 February 2020).

5. Conclusion

This study was conducted in Bahir Dar Zuria Woreda to examine the practices and challenges of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes. The findings indicate that these mechanisms, particularly Shimglina, are widely practiced and play a significant role in resolving land disputes within the community. Various forms of Shimglina institutions are used to address different types of land disputes to ensure peaceful dispute settlements and foster communal harmony. These issues include those related to land ownership, boundary trespasses, land inheritance, donations, land transfers, sharecropping, plant shade, drainage direction, divorce-related land disputes, livestock crop destruction, grazing land disputes, access to pathways, squatting on communal lands, and land grabbing.

Shimglina's effectiveness in resolving rural land disputes is particularly beneficial for economically disadvantaged communities. Its strengths include cost-effectiveness, the ability to mend broken relationships through forgiveness, consensus-based participation in the dispute resolution process, timely and speedy resolution, local accessibility, and complementary services to government efforts. However, the study also highlights several challenges faced by Shimglina customary conflict resolution

mechanisms. These challenges include the absence of incentives for elders and religious leaders, the lack of legally recognized enforcement mechanisms for their decisions, low governmental support and recognition, government influence, and the politicization of Shimglina.

As such, as the examination of the effectiveness of the Shimglina demonstrates, the regional and local governments could utilize this local dispute resolution mechanism for fostering harmonious relationships with the locals and among the locals, as it offers an efficient means of addressing disputes. Additionally, community members should continue to value and utilize Shimglina, which aligns with their cultural traditions of peace, economic activity, and social organization. Emphasizing the historical and political significance of these customary conflict resolution systems can promote mutual support and reinforce harmonious coexistence in the community.

6. Acknowledgement

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7. Key Vernacular Terms

Debo: A customary mechanism of performing agricultural tasks together.

Derg: The Military Council ruled over Ethiopia from 1974-1991.

Giligil: Conforms to a kind of amicable process of dispute resolution.

Iddir: A customary institution used for ceremonial of sorrow.

Irq: The term Irq is the Amharic translation of the term conciliation.

Kebele: It is the lowest unit of local government in Ethiopia.

Mahiber: An association which is organized for the feast of saints such as St. Michael.

Mehala: An oath and swearing.

Sembete: A religious based practice mainly on the Sabbath day.

Shimglina: This literally means elderliness, denotes dispute solution by elderly persons.

Wodaje: A kind of established good relationship with individuals.

Woreda: It is an administrative division of a local government in Ethiopia that is equivalent to a district.

Yetut lij: A kind of adoption to be relatives based on the religious practices of orthodox Christianity.

Yezemed danginia: Settling disputes by the relatives of the disputants.

Yekirstina lij: A relationship created through God parenthood based on orthodox Christianity.

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9. Appendices

Data Collection Tools

INTERVIEW GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR RURAL COMMUNITY *SHIMAGELES* (ELDERS)

1. How do you explain rural land and rural land related disputes in your community?
2. What are the causes of rural land disputes?
3. What is the most emerging cause of rural land dispute?
4. What are the types of rural land disputes?
5. What are the most frequently observed types of rural land disputes?
6. What are the impacts of rural land disputes?
7. Who are the major actors involved in rural land disputes?
8. What is the dynamics of rural land and rural land related disputes?
9. What are the institutions of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute within your communities?
10. What are the practices of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land dispute?
11. What are the procedures of customary conflict resolution in resolving rural land dispute?
12. What are the rituals in settling rural land disputes through customary mechanisms within community?
13. What makes different the settlement of rural land disputes through customary conflict resolution mechanisms and in the formal system?
14. How do you describe the effectiveness of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
15. What are the weaknesses or disadvantage of customary conflict resolution system in rural land dispute settlement?
16. How the government supports or promotes for the development and effectiveness of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in settling rural land disputes?
17. What challenges are observed in the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
18. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?
19. How do you explain the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
20. What measures will be taken if the decision made by the customary mechanism is rejected by one of the disputants?
21. What are the enforcement mechanisms for the decisions made by customary conflict resolution?

INTERVIEW GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR RURAL RELIGIOUS LEADERS

1. How do you explain rural land and rural land related disputes in your community?
2. What are the causes of rural land disputes?
3. What is the most emerging cause of rural land disputes?
4. What are the types of rural land disputes?
5. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?
6. What are the impacts of rural land disputes?
7. What is the dynamics of rural land disputes?
8. What are the institutions of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute within your communities?
9. What are the procedures of customary conflict resolution in resolving rural land dispute?
10. What are the rituals?

11. What makes different the settlement of rural land disputes through customary conflict resolution mechanisms and in the formal systems?
12. How do you describe the effectiveness of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
13. How the government supports or promotes for the development and effectiveness of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in settling rural land disputes?
14. What challenges are observed in the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
15. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?
16. How do you explain the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
17. What measures will be taken if the decision made by the customary mechanism is refused by one of the disputants?
18. What are the enforcement mechanisms for the decisions passed by customary conflict resolution?

INTERVIEW GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR FARMERS WHO SETTLED THEIR RURAL LAND DISPUTES THROUGH CUSTOMARY CONFLICT RESOLUTION MECHANISMS

1. How do you explain rural land disputes in your community?
2. What are the causes of rural land disputes?
3. What are the types of rural land dispute?
4. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?
5. What are the impacts of rural land dispute?
6. What are the institutions of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
7. What are the impacts of rural land dispute?
8. What are the practices of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land dispute?
9. What makes different the settlement of rural land disputes through customary conflict resolution mechanisms and in the formal system?
10. What are the procedures of customary conflict resolution in resolving rural land dispute?
11. What are the contributions of settling rural land dispute through customary conflict resolution mechanisms?
12. How the government supports or promotes for the development and effectiveness of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in settling rural land disputes?
13. How do you evaluate the effectiveness of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
14. What challenges are observed in the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
15. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?
16. What are the weaknesses of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
17. How do you explain the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
18. What measures are taken if the decision made by the customary mechanism is refused by one of the disputants?
19. What are the enforcement mechanisms for the decisions passed by customary conflict resolution?

INTERVIEW GUIDELINE QUESTION FOR WOREDA COURT JUDGES

1. How do you explain rural land disputes in your Woreda community?
2. Which types of rural land disputes cases do you receive from the rural people and the reasons for the disputes?
3. What are the most frequently observed causes of rural land disputes?
4. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?

5. What is the dynamics of rural land disputes?
6. How the court give recognition for the settlement of rural land disputes through customary systems?
7. To what extent the decisions of customary conflict resolution are acceptable by the court?

INTERVIEW GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR WOREDA RURAL LAND ADMINISTRATION AND USE EXPERTS

1. How do you explain rural land disputes in your Woreda community?
2. What are the causes of rural land and rural land related disputes?
3. What is the most emerging cause of rural land disputes?
4. What are the most common types of rural land disputes that frequently observed in your Woreda?
5. Who are the actors in rural land disputes in your Woreda?
6. What is the dynamics of rural land disputes in your Woreda?
7. What are the impacts of rural land disputes?

INTERVIEW GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR KEBELE RURAL LAND ADMINISTRATION AND USE EXPERTS

1. How do you explain rural land disputes in your kebele community?
2. What are the causes of rural land disputes?
3. What is the most emerging cause of rural land disputes?
4. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?
5. What are the types of rural land disputes?
6. What are the most common types of rural land disputes frequently observed in your kebele?
7. What was the dynamics of rural land disputes?
8. What are the impacts of rural land disputes in your kebele?
9. How rural land disputes are resolved in your kebele?
10. What makes different customary dispute resolution in rural land dispute and in the formal systems?
11. What is the preference of the disputant in resolving their rural land dispute? Customary or the formal system? Why?

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR THE REGIONAL RURAL LAND ADMINISTRATION AND USE EXPERTS

1. How do you explain the regional government engagement with customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
2. How the government supports or promotes customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes?
3. What are polices or strategies in the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes? Is there an institutional framework in the application of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR RURAL COMMUNITY ELDERS (*Shimageles*)

1. How do you explain rural land disputes in your community?
2. What are the causes of the disputes?
3. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?
4. What is the dynamics of rural land disputes in your community?
5. What is the preference of the disputant in resolving their rural land dispute? Customary or the formal system? Why?
6. What are the institutions of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in your community used to resolve rural land disputes?
7. What are the procedures of the practices of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
8. What are the rituals in settling rural land disputes?

9. What makes different customary dispute resolution in rural land dispute and the formal system?
10. What are the challenges of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
11. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?
12. What are the weaknesses in customary conflict resolutions of rural land dispute?
13. What is the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes?
14. How the government supports the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
15. What are the impacts of rural land disputes in your community?

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR FARMERS WHO SETTLE THEIR RURAL LAND DISPUTE THROUGH CUSTOMARY CONFLICT RESOLUTION MECHANISMS

1. How do you explain rural land disputes and rural land related disputes?
2. What was the cause of the disputes?
3. What are the institutions of customary conflict mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
4. What are the practices of customary conflict resolution to settle rural land disputes?
5. What are the rituals in rural land disputes resolution?
6. What makes different customary dispute resolution in rural land dispute and in the formal systems?
7. What is the preference of the disputant in resolving their rural land dispute? Customary or the formal system? Why?
8. What is the strength of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes?
9. What are the weaknesses in customary conflict resolutions of rural land dispute?
10. What are the challenges of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
11. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?
12. What is the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land disputes?
13. How the government supports or promotes the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION GUIDELINE QUESTIONS FOR THE ELDERLY ARBITRATION COMMITTEE (*YE SHIMAGLEWOCH SHENGO*) OF RURAL LAND DISPUTES

1. How do you explain rural land disputes in the community?
2. What are the causes of the rural land and rural land related disputes?
3. What are the types of rural land disputes?
4. What are the most frequently observed cause of rural land disputes?
5. What is the dynamics of rural land and land related disputes in your kebele?
6. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?
7. What are the impacts of rural land disputes?
8. How rural land disputes are settled though customary conflict resolution mechanisms?
9. What are the procedures in resolving rural land disputes through customary conflict resolution?
10. What are the rituals?
11. What makes different customary dispute resolution in rural land dispute and in the formal systems?
12. What is the preference of the disputant in resolving their rural land dispute? Why?

13. What is the strength of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes?
14. How the government supports or promotes the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
15. What are the weaknesses in customary conflict resolutions of rural land dispute?
16. What is the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes?
17. What are the challenges of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
18. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?

Focus Group Discussion Guideline Questions for the Kebele Rural Land Administration and Use Committee

1. How do you explain rural land disputes?
2. What are the causes of rural land disputes in your kebele?
3. What are the most frequently observed cause of rural land disputes?
4. What types of rural land disputes are exist in your kebele?
5. Who are the actors in rural land disputes?
6. How rural land disputes are resolved in this community?
7. What was the role of the customary system in rural land disputes?
8. What is the dynamics of rural land disputes?
9. What is the impact of rural land dispute in your kebele?

Interview Guideline Questions for Farmers Who settled their Land Disputes in Customary Conflict Resolution

1. How do you explain rural land disputes and rural land related disputes?
2. What was the cause of the disputes?
3. What are the institutions of customary conflict mechanisms in resolving rural land dispute?
4. What are the practices of customary conflict resolution to settle rural land disputes?
5. What are the rituals in rural land disputes resolution?
6. What makes different customary dispute resolution in rural land dispute and in the formal systems?
7. What is the preference of the disputant in resolving their rural land dispute? Customary or the formal system? Why?
8. What is the strength of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in rural land disputes?
9. What are the weaknesses in customary conflict resolutions of rural land dispute?
10. What are the challenges of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?
11. What do you think should be done in the future to reduce the challenges?
12. What is the current status of customary conflict resolution mechanisms in resolving rural land disputes?
13. How the government supports or promotes the practice of customary conflict resolution in rural land disputes?

Author's Declarations and Essential Ethical Compliances

Authors' Contributions (in accordance with ICMJE criteria for authorship)

This article is 100% contributed by the sole author. He conceived and designed the research or analysis, collected the data, contributed to data analysis & interpretation, wrote the article, performed critical revision of the article/paper, edited the article, and supervised and administered the field work.

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Research involving human bodies or organs or tissues (Helsinki Declaration)

The author(s) solemnly declare(s) that this research has not involved any human subject (body or organs) for experimentation. It was not a clinical research. The contexts of human population/participation were only indirectly covered through literature review. Therefore, an Ethical Clearance (from a Committee or Authority) or ethical obligation of Helsinki Declaration does not apply in cases of this study or written work.

Research involving animals (ARRIVE Checklist)

The author(s) solemnly declare(s) that this research has not involved any animal subject (body or organs) for experimentation. The research was not based on laboratory experiment involving any kind animal. The contexts of animals were only indirectly covered through literature review. Therefore, an Ethical Clearance (from a Committee or Authority) or ethical obligation of ARRIVE does not apply in cases of this study or written work.

Research on Indigenous Peoples and/or Traditional Knowledge

The author(s) solemnly declare(s) that this research has not involved Indigenous Peoples as participants or respondents. The contexts of Indigenous Peoples or Indigenous Knowledge were only indirectly covered through literature review. Therefore, an Ethical Clearance (from a Committee or Authority) or prior informed consent (PIC) of the respondents or Self-Declaration in this regard does not apply in cases of this study or written work.

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The author(s) solemnly declare(s) that this research has not involved the plants for experiment and field studies. Some contexts of plants are also indirectly covered through literature review. Thus, during this research the author(s) obeyed the principles of the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Convention on the Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora.

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PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)

The author(s) has/have NOT complied with PRISMA standards. It is not relevant in case of this study or written work.

Competing Interests/Conflict of Interest

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